

Evaluation of the protective effect of curcuma extract against Methotrexate induced genotoxicity

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Abstract

The present study aimed to evaluate the antigenotoxic activity of curcumin, a yellow colouring agent, contained in turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L., Zingiberaceae) on male rats. Curcumin possesses anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, therefore, it has been extensively investigated for its cancer chemopreventive potential. Eighty *Swiss albino* male allocated in several groups treated with methotrexate (MTX, 10 mg/kg b.w.) and/or Curcumin (0.5, 10 and 25 mg/kg b.w). Random amplified polymorphic DNA polymerase chain reaction (RAPD-PCR) was used to determine the genetic damage in rats due to MTX and/or Curcumin treatment. Twenty random 10-nucleotide primers were used to determine the DNA damage and to perform the genotoxic and antimutagenic activity of the curcumin. Results showed that treatment of rats with low dose of curcumin alone did not induce any genotoxic effects. Supplementation of MTX treated-rats with 0.5 mg/kg bw of the curcumin reduced the DNA induced by MTX. However, continuous treatments with 10 and 25 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin induced DNA damage either alone or in combination with MTX treatment. Based on these findings we conclude that curcumin shows both genotoxicity and antigenotoxicity in a dose-depending manner.

Keywords

Methotrexate, Curcumin, DNA damage, RAPD-PCR, male rats

Introduction

Methotrexate (MTX), a folic acid antagonist, is widely used as a cytotoxic chemotherapeutic agent for treatment of leukemias and other malignancies [1]. In addition, it has been used for the treatment of various inflammatory diseases such as psoriasis and rheumatoid arthritis. However, the efficacy of this agent in high doses has been associated with hepatotoxicity [1]. Substantial evidence supports the concept that methotrexate was mutagenic and carcinogenic in animals [2]. The genotoxic effect of anticancerous drugs may be reduced if supplemented with natural antioxidants plant products.

A wide variety of phenolic compounds derived from edible plants have been reported to retain marked anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, which contribute to their chemopreventive potential [3,4]. Among these compounds, curcumin, it is a yellow odorless pigment isolated from the rhizome of tumeric (*Curcuma Longa* L., zingiberaceae). Pharmacological studies have demonstrated its anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant activity with very low toxicity [5,6]. Also, anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory effects of this compound have been assessed in various *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental animal systems, human studies and on other living organisms [7,8]. The practice of disease prevention is the most cost effective means for improving human health. The prolonged use of the anticancer drugs may result in various types of secondary tumors in normal cells. Anticancer drug e.g. mitomycin C is a potent DNA cross-linker [9].

Despite reported benefits, *in vitro* studies in cultured cells have demonstrated that curcumin induces chromosomal or DNA damage detected by the comet assay [10,11]. To explain this *in vitro* effect, it was proposed that curcumin can also act as pro-oxidant.

Therefore the aim of the present study was to evaluate the effect of curcumin against the genotoxic impacts of methotrexate in rats.

Material and Methods

Chemicals: Methotrexate was purchased from sigma U.S.A. Random primer kits (A, B, C and D) were purchased from Operon Technologies (Alameda, CA, USA). All reagents and chemicals were of the highest purity.

Animals: Eighty *Swiss albino* male rats (100-125g) were purchased from the animal house colony, King Abdelaziz University, (Jeddah, Saudi Arabia). Rats were maintained on standard laboratory diet (protein, 16.04%, fat, 3.63%, fiber, 4.1 % and metabolic energy, 0.012 MJ) and water. After an acclimation period of a week, animals were divided into eight groups (10 rats group), housed individually in filter-top polycarbonate cages housed in a temperature-controlled (23 ± 1 °C) and artificially illuminated (12 h dark/ light cycle) room free from any source of chemical contamination. All animals received human care in compliance with the guidelines of the animal care and use committee of the King Abdelaziz University animal house.

Experimental Design: Animals within different treatments groups were treated (daily at a 24-h interval) intragastrically for 37 days as follows: First

group contained rats kept untreated as the control group. Second to fourth groups contained rats treated with 0.5, 10 and 25 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin, respectively. Fifth to seventh groups contained rats treated similar to groups 2 to 4, respectively, plus intraperitoneally single dose of 10mg/kg b.w. of methotrexate on the last day of curcumin treatment. Eighth group contained rats treated with single dose of 10 mg/kg b. w. of methotrexate alone at the 37th day of the treatment.

At the end of the experimental period, all animals were sacrificed and dissected on day 38. Liver tissue samples were collected from all animals for Random amplified polymorphic DNA polymerase chain reaction (RAPD PCR) [12].

RAPD-PCR assay

The genomic DNA was isolated using phenol/chloroform extraction and ethanol precipitation method with minor modifications [13,14].

RAPD-PCR profiles from male rats DNA were generated using 20 primers (10-mer random primers, Table 1) from Operon Technologies (Alameda, CA, USA). DNA amplification reactions were performed under conditions reported by Luceri et al. (2000) [15]. PCR amplification was conducted in 50 µl reaction volume containing 100 ng genomic DNA; 100 µM dNTPs; 40 nm primer; 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase and 5 µl promega 10X Taq DNA polymerase buffer. The reactions were carried out in a thermocycler (Perkin-Elmer 9700) programmed first for denaturation of 5 min at 94 °C, followed by 45 cycles of 0.5 min at 94 °C, 1 min at 36 °C and 2 min at 72 °C and finally, one cycle at 72 °C for 5 min. The PCR product was analysed by electrophoresing 15 µl of the amplified mixture on agarose gel [16,17,18,19]. The Gel-Pro Analyzer (Media Cybernetics) was used to document ethidium bromide DNA gels.

Table 1: Sequence of primers employed

Primer	Sequence	Primer	Sequence
A01	5'-CAGGCCCTTC-3'	C03	5'-GGGGGTCTTT-3'
A02	5'-TGCCGAGCTG-3'	C05	5'-GATGACCGCC-3'
A03	5'-AGTCAGCCAC-3'	C07	5'-GTCCCGACGA-3'
A04	5'-AATCGGGCTG-3'	C09	5'-CTCACCGTCC-3'
A05	5'-AGGGGTCTTG-3'	C12	5'-TGTCATCCCC-3'
A10	5'-GTGATCGCAG-3'	C15	5'-GACGGATCAG-3'
A12	5'-TCGGCGATAG-3'	C20	5'-ACTTCGCCAC-3'
A15	5'-TTCCGAACCC-3'	D01	5'-ACCGGAAGG-3'
A20	5'-GTTGCGATCC-3'	D03	5'-GTCGCCGTC-3'
B14	5'-TCCGCTCTGG-3'	D04	5'-TCGACTCTGG-3'

Statistical Analysis

The pictures have been taken by Lap image to show the mutation activity and anti-mutagenicity. Comparison the results were carried out using Dendrogram graphic to illustrate the results and determine the changes in the genetic material chart. This analysis is based on the average coherence between the totals and through the use of Cluster analysis. All the grouped data were evaluated with

SPSS/19 software. The data were expressed as mean ± S.E with the 10 animals in each group.

Results

RAPD fingerprinting assay

The molecular genetic variability among the treated rats and their control were evaluated using 4 random primer kits (A, B, C and D). Only twelve of these primers (10-mer random primers, Table 1) gave positive and detectable bands (Figures 1-3).

Figure 1 Comparison of RAPD fingerprinting profiles of different male rats genomic DNA treated with curcumin for 37 days. a) Represents PCR products with primer A01; b) represents PCR products with primer A02; c) represents PCR products with primer A03; and d) represents PCR products with primer A04; e) represents PCR products with primer A05; f) represents PCR products with primer B14. The DNA marker was in lanes 1 and 10. Lane 2 represents PCR products of untreated control samples; lane 3 represents rats treated with 0.5 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 4 represents rats treated with 10 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 5 represents rats treated with 25 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 6, 7 and 8 similar to lanes 3, 4 and 5, respectively, plus single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX; lane 9 represents rats treated with single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX.

The primers used provided a total of 253 different bands with an average of 20.91 ± 1.6 bands per primer (Table 2). Nearly the same results were obtained when the PCR assay was performed for each sample within each group (10 animals). Treatment of animals with curcumin at the low (0.5 mg/kg b.w.) dose did not cause any damage on the DNA compared to control rats. Moreover, medium (10 mg/kg b.w.) and high (25 mg/kg b.w.) caused slightly changes in the DNA structures compared to control rats. Where, most of the bands (174 bands, 68.77%) resulted from all primers (A01, A02, A03, A04, A05, B14, C03, C05, C06, C07, C09 and D06) were monomorphic for the control and curcumin treated animals (Figures 1-3).

Figure 2 Comparison of RAPD fingerprinting profiles of different male rats genomic DNA treated with curcumin for 37 days. a) Represents PCR products with primer C03; b) represents PCR products with primer C05; c) represents PCR products with primer C06; and d) represents PCR products with primer C07; e) represents PCR products with primer C09; f) represents PCR products with primer D06. The DNA marker was in lanes 1 and 10. Lane 2 represents PCR products of untreated control samples; lane 3 represents rats treated with 0.5 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 4 represents rats treated with 10 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 5 represents rats treated with 25 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 6, 7 and 8 similar to lanes 3, 4 and 5, respectively, plus single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX; lane 9 represents rats treated with single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX.

Figure 3 Comparison of RAPD fingerprinting profiles of different male rats genomic DNA treated with curcumin for 37 days. a) Represents PCR products with primer A12; b) represents PCR products with primer A15; c) represents PCR products with primer A20; d) represents PCR products with primer C12; e) represents PCR products with primer C15; f) represents PCR products with primer C20; g) represents PCR

products with primer D01; h) represents PCR products with primer D03. The DNA marker was in lanes 1 and 10. Lane 2 represents PCR products of untreated control samples; lane 3 represents rats treated with 0.5 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 4 represents rats treated with 10 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 5 represents rats treated with 25 mg/kg b.w. of curcumin; lane 6, 7 and 8 similar to lanes 3, 4 and 5, respectively, plus single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX; lane 9 represents rats treated with single dose of 10 mg/kg b.w. of MTX.

Table 2: Size in base pair of detected markers

Marker	Curcumin				Curcumin + MTX			
	Control	Cu ^{0.5}	Cu ¹⁰	Cu ²⁵	Control	Cu ^{0.5}	Cu ¹⁰	Cu ²⁵
A01-798	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-796	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-794	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-692	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-661	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-641	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-596	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-529	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-526	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-515	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-488	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-428	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-412	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-395	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-325	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-243	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-223	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-214	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-196	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-176	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A01-119	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A02-998	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-1198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-1140	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-1122	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-1023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-1003	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-999	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-889	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-978	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-957	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-718	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-704	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-517	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-380	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-284	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A03-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A04-492	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A04-450	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A04-403	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A04-382	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A04-1002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Cu^{0.5} Curcumin (0.5 mg/kg); Cu¹⁰ Curcumin (10 mg/kg); Cu²⁵ Curcumin (25 mg/kg); MTX, melatonin

Table 2: Continue

Marker	Curcumin				Curcumin + MTX			
	Control	Cu ^{0.5}	Cu ¹⁰	Cu ²⁵	Control	Cu ^{0.5}	Cu ¹⁰	Cu ²⁵
A05-837	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-496	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-485	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-441	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-428	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-412	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-405	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-347	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-341	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-322	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-246	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-242	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-222	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-86	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
A05-756	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4548	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4198	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4180	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4023	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4020	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4002	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-390	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-378	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-360	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-349	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-317	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-300	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-298	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-296	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-280	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-254	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-190	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-184	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-89	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-499	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4145	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B14-4299	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

the germ cells in male swiss mice. Furthermore, Padmanabhan et al. (2008) [24] reported that treatment of male Swiss mice with the doses of 5, 10, 20 and 40 mg/kg of MTX induced DNA damage assessed by comet assay. In addition, they found that MTX caused toxicity and genotoxicity in germ cell of male mice.

The underlying mechanism of hepatotoxicity caused by MTX treatment needs more explanation to be understood. It has been reported that MTX causes oxidative stress in liver tissue [1]. Although 7-OH metabolite is the major pathway of MTX metabolism, MTX is metabolized and stored in hepatocytes in the polyglutamated form [25]. The presence of higher levels of polyglutamates causes a longer intracellular presence of the drug and this has been suggested as a mechanism for hepatotoxicity [1]. Moreover, MTX inhibits dihydrofolate reductase which indirectly affects the synthesis of thymidilate, thereby suppressing DNA synthesis [1]. Additionally, it was demonstrated that the cytosolic nicotinamide adenosine diphosphate (NADP)-dependent dehydrogenases and NADP malic enzyme are inhibited by MTX, suggesting that the drug could decrease the availability of NADPH in cells [26]. Under normal conditions, NADPH is used by glutathione reductase to maintain the reduced state of cellular glutathione, an important cytosolic antioxidant, which protects against reactive oxygen species (ROS). Thus the significant reduction in glutathione (GSH) levels induced by MTX leads to reduction in the level of the antioxidant enzymes and consequently the immune system, e.g, sensitizing the cells to ROS [27].

Curcumin is a yellow pigment present in the rhizome of turmeric (*Curcuma Longa L.*, Zingiberaceae). It possesses anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [4]. Curcumin also acts as a single oxygen quencher [28].

in vivo studies on curcumin supplementation suggest that no genotoxicity or clastogenicity was found due to its antioxidant activity. These studies were carried out using several analyses such as chromosome aberrations, micronuclei, somatic mutations and recombination assays [29,30,31].

In contrary to the previous antioxidant nature findings of curcuminoids, much evidence for cytotoxic properties of curcumin was reported and suggested to be due to production of reactive oxygen species and causes oxidative DNA damage [32]. In consistent, our current molecular genetics findings demonstrated that the exposure to high dose of curcumin induced DNA damage in liver cells of male rats.

The current results revealed that treatment of male rats with curcumin induced damage in the DNA in dose depending manner (e.g., the high dose, 25 mg/kg) treatment. In agreement with our results, Cao et al. (2007) [33] reported that curcumin induced both genotoxicity and anti-genotoxicity depending on its concentration. They found that curcumin affects the formation of MN. Where, curcumin at the high doses (8 and 16 µg/ml) displayed a small but

significant increase in the frequency of MN. However, they found that the low dose of curcumin (2 µg/ml) significantly reduced the MN formation induced by the chemotherapeutic agent. The comet assay showed that incubation of N18 cells with 10, 25 and 30 µM of curcumin caused DNA damage and inhibited DNA repair genes which may be the factors for curcumin-inhibited cell growth [34].

Furthermore, combination between curcumin and MTX in the present study did not inhibit the DNA damage completely. Where, in the present study treatment of male rats with 10mg/kg of MTX plus curcumin was able to induce damage in the DNA. These findings agreed the results of Hassanane et al. (2010) [35], who reported that combined treatment between curcumin and MTX in dose of 0.5, 10 and 20 mg/kg was accompanied with induction in the DNA damage.

On the other hand, curcumin treatment is still effective against many heavy metals and mutagenic drugs. *in vivo* curcumin treatment exerted a protective effect against copper genotoxicity which this role was evaluated by the comet and micronucleus assays [36]. In addition, Song et al. (2008) [37] reported that curcumin revealed protective effect against MTX in rats. Despite, MTX induced an increase in the mucosal permeability of the small intestines in rats, curcumin revealed protective effects against MTX-induced rat enteritis by lowering the intestinal mucosal permeability. Moreover, curcumin suppressed the effect of MTX induced toxicity in the intestinal epithelial cells when it used as anticancer drug. Treatment with curcumin at the concentration of 2.5 µg/mL significantly reduced acrylamide effect-induced DNA fragmentation, micronuclei formation, and cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells [38,39,40].

The protective effect of curcumin against several heavy metals and mutagenic drugs still needs more interpretations. Iqbal et al. (2003) [41] indicated that curcumin activates detoxifying enzymes, such as antioxidant and phase II enzymes in mouse liver and kidneys, acting as a protective agent against chemical carcinogenesis and other forms of electrophilic toxicity. Also, curcumin can be metabolized into tetrahydrocurcumin, which may have greater antioxidant, antimutagenic or antitumor effects than curcumin [42]. Barik et al. (2005) [43] demonstrated that copper-curcumin complexes show superoxide dismutase-like activity, acting as free radical scavengers and antioxidants. Curcumin *in vivo* exerts a global antioxidant effect, but *in vitro* increased genomic damage has been also reported [10,11,44].

In conclusion, curcumin was able to inhibit the genotoxicity effect of MTX in male rats. However, curcumin shows both genotoxicity and antigenotoxicity in dose depending manner.

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